

ANALYSIS OF BUCKLING LOAD OF FIBER-REINFORCED PLYWOOD PLATES

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1 Introduction

Over the last few years, there has been an increased usage of fiber-reinforced composite (FRC) materials in many areas such as structure applications, including rehabilitation and retrofitting, mainly due to superior high strength properties, low weight and corrosion resistance of FRC. Plywood is one of the most widely used materials in a number of light weight applications in the many industries such as construction, shipbuilding etc. A number of different tests have been carried out over the past few decades such as shear reinforcement of wood using FRP (Triantafillou, 1997), characteristics of high strength FRP reinforcement of wood (Tingley and Cengelka, 1996), and testing of rectangular composite plates of dynamic pulse buckling (Ari-Gur and Simonetta, 1997). This paper presents an experimental investigation of buckling load of plywood plates reinforced with various types of glass fiber composite materials. Plywood laminated with FRC fabrics provide a superior composite which is light and has significantly improving buckling load characteristics compared to untreated plywood material.

2 Experimental

2.1 Experimental condition

Buckling tests were conducted using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) for thick structural plywood plate reinforced with glass/epoxy composite. The two ends of the plates were fixed to the UTM with compression jig which is designed to compress the material. The plywood plate reinforced with glass/epoxy composite consists of plywood with dimensions 300 x 80 x 9 mm and glass fiber prepreg. The mechanical properties of plywood and glass fiber is shown in the table.1

material	Plywood	Glass fiber prepreg
Em,1 [MPa]	9450	35400
Em,2 [MPa]	8000	5000
Em3 [MPa]	820	5000
Gm,12 [MPa]	790	3500
Gm,13 [MPa]	325	3500
Gm,23 [MPa]	260	3500
v12 [-]	0.1	0.25
v13 [-]	0.1	0.25
v23 [-]	0.1	0.25
density	550	190

Table.1. Material properties

Buckling tests were conducted using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) for thick structural plywood plate reinforced with glass/epoxy composite. The two ends of the plates were fixed to the UTM with compression jig which is designed to compress the material. The plywood plate reinforced with glass/epoxy composite consists of plywood with dimensions 300 x 80 x 9 mm and glass fiber prepreg. The mechanical properties of plywood and glass fiber is shown in the table.1

2.2 Theoretical background

The buckling is a mathematical instability, leading to a failure mode. Theoretically, buckling is characterized by a sudden failure of a structural member subjected to high compressive stress, where the actual compressive stress at the point of failure is less than the ultimate compressive stresses that the material is capable of withstanding. The maximum load, sometimes called the critical load,

$$F = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{(KL)^2} \quad (1)$$

where F is maximum or critical force (vertical load on column), E is modulus of elasticity, I is area moment of inertia, L is unsupported length of column, K is column effective length factor. Especially, K value depends on the conditions of end support of the column. Experiments were conducted under both ends fixed condition, Therefore K is 0.50.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Results

The graph of results is presented in Fig.1, which shows compressive buckling load with compressive displacement. The black graph shows the theoretical load, and blue graph represents experimental value for each buckling test. First graph shows buckling behavior for the untreated plywood, second is for reinforced with 0.054 mm, the third is for 0.108 mm, the fourth is for 0.162 mm, and the fifth is for 0.216 mm glass fiber, respectively. For reinforce with 0.054 mm, 0.108 mm, 0.162 mm, 0.216 mm glass fiber, the critical buckling strength has increased by about 10.43%, 21.12%, 30.07%, 43.29%, respectively, compared to the untreated plate. These results show that higher buckling load as well as lightweight can be achieved using external fiber reinforcement. The failure is also shown differently for each fiber. The untreated plywood tends to fail catastrophically.

Fig.1. buckling load for untreated plywood

Fig.2. buckling load for reinforced with 0.054 mm glass fiber prepreg

Fig.3. buckling load for reinforced with 0.108 mm glass fiber prepreg

Fig.4. buckling load for reinforced with 0.162 mm glass fiber prepreg

Fig.5. buckling load for reinforced with 0.216 mm glass fiber prepreg

However, fiber reinforced plywood tends to fail with stage failure. The failure is also shown differently for each fiber.

4. Conclusion

Plywood plate with glass fiber reinforcement produces a superior composite material that could be used to enhance the load such as buckling compressive load. These tests indicate that the reinforced plywood plates perform much higher buckling load under compressive loads. This means that much higher load can be applied using glass

fiber reinforced material. By using reinforced plywood, the number of plywood plate can be reduced in NO 96 insulation box to support external sloshing load.

Furthermore, more study reflected with temperature effect will be done due to cryogenic condition of LNG. Heat transfer always happens in the insulation box, so buckling result should be considered with cryogenic temperature. Further experiments should be added in the buckling test.

experimental result (mean) (N)		Theoretical value (N)
Untreated	16203.75	16000.00
1 Sheet	17639.89	17669.56
2 Sheets	19516.82	19379.78
3 Sheets	21035.70	21131.69
4 Sheets	23408.67	22926.28

	Increment of strength (%)
Untreated	
1 Sheet	8.86
2 Sheets	20.45
3 Sheets	29.82
4 Sheets	44.46

Table.2. The critical buckling load for each case and increment of critical buckling strength

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